

THERMOCHEMICAL RECYCLING OF POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE: EXPERIMENTAL AND KINETIC INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

In a circular economy perspective, Plastic Wastes (PW) are a valuable source of chemicals, energy vectors and fuels. Thermochemical recycling technologies as pyrolysis, gasification and partial oxidation are promising processes, which require the definition of suitable condensed phase pyrolysis kinetic models. While mechanical and other chemical recycling technologies are well established for polyethylene terephthalate (PET), thermochemical recycling allows to treat complex and contaminated mixtures. This work proposes a semi-detailed kinetic model for PET pyrolysis based on a consolidated functional group approach and suitable for CFD simulations. The model is validated by a comprehensive set of literature experimental data and new GCxGC speciation data. The present work extends the CRECK kinetic framework for thermochemical recycling of PW mixtures.

Introduction

Waste valorization through chemical recycling is a key step towards circular and sustainable chemical and energy industries. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) is among the main constituents of Plastic Waste (PW) mixtures due to its widespread use in packaging, fiber production, film applications and in the manufacturing or automotive industry. Several recycling technologies have been developed in the past decades [1], but they involve significant purification and separation costs while, in some cases, also deteriorating the material properties. In this context, thermochemical recycling is a complementary alternative for complex and polluted wastes through waste-to-chemicals processes such as pyrolysis or gasification technologies. To this aim, chemical kinetics and fluid dynamics tool can aid in reactor optimization tailoring the product distribution [2,3].

The kinetics of PET thermal degradation have received less attention compared to other polymers. Several reaction mechanisms have been proposed [4–6], but, to the

authors knowledge, only simple global models have been developed. This work proposes a semi-detailed kinetic model for PET pyrolysis following the functional group approach employed for polyolefins and biomass pyrolysis [7] widening the subset of polymers kinetic models available in the CRECK framework. Model validation, both in terms of mass-loss and product distribution profiles, is performed by comparison with literature experimental data. Additionally, new micro-pyrolysis speciation data by two-dimensional GC are presented.

Methods and Materials

A virgin commercial PET sample is employed for all experimental measurements. The elemental CHNS/O composition of the polymer was analysed with a Thermo Scientific FLASH 2000 analyzer. Five replicates were performed burning 2–3 mg of sample in pure oxygen at 950 °C. An elemental composition of $63.74 \pm 1.09\%$ wt C and $4.23 \pm 0.03\%$ wt H is measured, where no nitrogen or sulphur is detected.

The pyrolysis experiments are performed in a micro-pyrolysis unit (Rx-3050 TR, Frontier Lab., Japan) coupled with a two-dimensional Gas Chromatography (GCxGC, Thermo Scientific TRACE Ultra) and a separate GC dedicated for analysis of light gases (Thermo Scientific Trace 1310) described in previous works [8,9]. Briefly, experiments are performed at 400, 500, and 600°C dropping 500–800 µg of materials into the preheated pyrolysis furnace. The reactor is operated with a He sweep flowrate of 50 mL/min and a pressure of ~2.7 bar. The released volatiles are collected in a cryo-trap (MJT-1035E) cooled with liquid nitrogen and then simultaneously fed to the two analysis system. The GC columns, an MXT-1 non-polar and a ZB-35HT polar, are operated from 40°C to 350°C with a ramp of 5°C/min. Compound identification is performed with a BenchTOF-Select™ (Markes, United Kingdom) scanning $m/z = 50-500$ at 70 eV comparing the products spectra with the NIST library database. Compound quantification is performed with an FID calibrated with iso-butane and response factors are calculated via the molecular response factor (MRF) method as reported by De Saint Laumer et al. [10]. Mass closure obtained from the setup increases with temperature, ranging from 30% at 400°C to 70% at 600°C. However, considering ~20 wt% of char formation [11,12], the results are deemed acceptable.

Kinetic Mechanism

According to the functional group approach, the polymer chain distribution is represented through pseudo-species characteristic of the chemical moieties of the polymer, while real species are employed to describe products of interest such as CO, CH₃CO, C₆H₅COOH or the monomers [7]. The starting polymer is characterized only by the terephthalic and ethylene glycol moieties (labelled respectively P-COC₆H₄CO-P and P-OC₂H₄O-P), but, during the degradation process, other groups are formed such as carboxylic acids, alcohols and terminal double bonds, and the corresponding pseudo-species are introduced as well.

The proposed kinetic mechanism stems from literature studies on plausible molecular pathways [4] and analogous radical degradation mechanisms developed for gas-phase oxygenated analogous compounds or lignin [13]. The first involve 6- and 4-member rings degrading in concerted pathways as shown in Figure 1, forming free polymer ends and cyclic oligomers.

Figure 1. Representation of the pseudo-species describing PET chains and their molecular concerted degradation mechanism

The radical degradation is the main decomposition pathway [5,6], responsible for formation of CO, CH₃CO, and biphenyl structures. Initiation occurs by random scission on the C-C or C-O bonds on the glycol moieties. The produced radicals then undergo propagation reactions such as H-abstractions, β-scissions, and radical additions. Only termination by radical-radical recombination is considered. As with polyvinylchloride and lignin, condensation and radical additions to the aromatic rings result in formation of considerable amounts of carbonaceous residues (char). All proposed reaction classes considerably affect the degradation mechanism. Reaction temperatures are mainly affected by β-scissions, which are the rate determining step, and random scission and recombination reactions, which control the radical pool. H-abstractions and additions affect the product distribution together with β-scissions reactions. The reaction mechanism involves only homogeneous liquid-phase reactions and evaporation is considered separately with appropriate mass-transfer exchange coefficients [3]. The proposed kinetic parameters are obtained from analogy to gas-phase reactions [13] and have similar selectivities to the ones proposed by Huang et al. [5] and Ma et al. [6]. Nevertheless, specific corrections for the transposition from gas to liquid are included [14].

Results

The proposed kinetic model is validated with a comprehensive set of experimental data from literature, both in terms of mass-loss profiles and gas-products distribution, in addition to the new experimental data provided herein. For sake of

brevity, only few comparisons for mass-loss profiles are shown in Figure 2. With respect to dynamic conditions, shown in Figure 2.a, the model proves able to capture correctly both onset temperatures and the differences resulting from different heating rates. Similarly, considering isothermal conditions reported in Figure 2.b, the model correctly describes the temperature effect. Nevertheless, further work is still required to improve predictions of char yields, although, to the authors' knowledge, only few characterization data are reported.

Figure 2. Comparison of predicted (lines) and measured (symbols) mass-loss at: a) constant heating rate [11]; b) isothermal conditions [15]

The main degradation products experimentally measured are shown in Figure 3. The most abundant compound is CO_2 , followed by benzoic acid, CO , and CH_3CHO . These results are in line with values reported by Dhahak et al. [4] at low temperatures and Day et al. [12] at higher temperatures. Nevertheless, no CO is detected at 400°C while terephthalic acid is identified at all temperatures. The reduction in its yield at higher temperature is consequent to formation of lower molecular weight compounds such as benzene and acetaldehyde. Similarly, the amounts of vinyl benzoate are comparable to measurements of Dhahak et al. but are lower than those by Day et al. (~ 30 wt%). Overall, the mass closure is poor at 400°C , although in line with Dhahak et al. [4]. The reason is possibly formation of long-chain products outside the detection range which decompose at higher temperatures [16].

Figure 3. Main volatiles experimentally measured at 400, 500, and 600°C.

Conclusions

The thermal degradation of PET has been investigated experimentally and a kinetic model has been proposed. Speciation data are obtained in a micro-pyrolysis unit coupled to a two-dimensional GC analyser. The model, based on a functional group approach, is validated also with literature experimental data proving able to describe both polymer mass evolution and the release of gas-phase products in a detailed fashion. Further experimental and modelling work are required to investigate char formation and mixture interactions. The present investigation constitutes an important step towards modelling the chemical recycle of plastic waste mixtures.

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